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PSYCHOLOGICAL IMPACT OF EXPLORATION OF
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PESHAWAR

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Psychological Impact of Exploration of Lived Patients Experiences Adjusting to Life after Esophageal Cancer in Peshawar

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Abstract

This study explores the psychological impact of adapting to life after esophageal cancer among patients in Peshawar, focusing on their lived experiences. It aims to understand the emotional, social, and mental health challenges faced by survivors as they transition from treatment to post-recovery life. Using a qualitative approach, in-depth interviews are conducted to capture personal narratives related to anxiety, depression, coping strategies, and changes in self-identity and daily functioning. The study highlights the role of family support, cultural context, and healthcare services in shaping patients' adjustment processes. The findings are expected to provide insights for healthcare professionals and policymakers to develop patient-

centered psychological support interventions, ultimately improving the quality of life for esophageal cancer survivors in the region. **Background:** Patients who have undergone esophagectomy for esophageal cancer experience fused physical, emotional, social, religious changes and financial challenges. In Pakistan Investigation of such changes and challenges from the patients' perspective have been conducted to a very limited extent which requires detail understanding to address the patients' problems in our context. **Objective:** The current study conducted for exploration of lived patients experiences adjusting to life after esophagectomy in public sector teaching hospital of Peshawar. **Methods:** A qualitative phenomenology design comprising individuals' in-depth interviews was used to collect data from patients at public sector teaching hospital Peshawar. Total participants interviewed were ten in numbers and method used for data analysis is thematic analysis. **Findings:** Mainly five problems were identified by participants including Physical changes, psychological

effects, social issues and support, financial issues, acceptance and adjustment to a new changed way of life. Survivors believed that their problems can be helped out with the support of government and society at large. **Conclusion:** Post-op esophageal cancer patients require full help in adjusting to their social, physical, emotional, financial and religious ways of life after esophagectomy. Family, friends, and society can be a blessing during the entire period of the disease. The government should provide financial and health care support to such patients for their treatment as well as for their rehabilitation.

Keywords: Post Operative, Psychological, Social, religious changes and financial challenges, esophageal

Introduction

1.1 Background

Esophagectomy for esophageal cancer treatment is a complex procedure with multiple complications and post-operation deaths (1,2) ranges from 1% to 5(3). Patients face multiple challenges and uneasiness as their role to live a completely normal life decrease afterward. They require the help of others physically, psychologically and emotionally (1,3). In cancer this type of cancer is the sixth cause of deaths in the world (4-6) because of its dangerous possible damages and poor chances of getting better (7,8). Each year it is the reason of about more than 400,000 deaths world wide (2,5,7).

In the United States of America, esophageal cancer in more than 12000 people gets diagnosed every year and the deaths ratio also the same (7). The fifth major cause of deaths in the United Kingdom is cancer of esophagus and cases of esophageal cancer has risen in last 25years and are rising continuously (4). This cancer is common in men than women and increases with the age (4,9) The large numbers of patients with esophageal cancer are reported in Iran, China, South Africa, and United States. The rate of cancer in these areas is more than 100 out of 100,000 populations (10). Whereas in Pakistan Karachi is marked as seventh common cancer in males and sixth in females(11), and in Peshawar 100 patients have undergone esophagectomy for esophageal cancer in a year in one center (12,13). Hot fluids, snuff, low intake of vegetables and fruits, use of alcohol and tobacco together in abundance are more common causes (6,14-16) and the patients generally suffer from symptoms such as pain, fatigue, dysphagia and weight loss (16) although, the early diagnosed esophageal cancer treatment is surgery called esophagectomy (16,17) but the rate of success of esophagectomy is low, it is 5 to 35% as the survival rate of such patients is about five years (7) because of dangerous damage, less chances of getting well and despite developments in surgical advancements successful rate of treatment result is not yet acquired in esophageal cancer patients (18).

Patients face many problems in their lives after surgery, as well as physical

and psychological problems and post-treatment effects that might be considered usual by health care providers(1). Patients with esophagectomy experience reduced life quality for long and need supportive care to deal with lives that are hanged due to number of long terms (16,19)constant physical effects creating considerable changes to eating behaviors and social activities(20). The support needs to be individualized and initiated at an early stage after surgery(16). Standard of nursing care has a relation with better treatment outcomes. Quality nursing care is important for successful patient-centered care(21). The nurses' role increased in cancer patient care. (22). Certain supportive care interventions have been developed with hopeful output(20). Before the development in the field of medicine and nursing most of the focus was on the patients' body and disease. The concept of nursing and medicine gradually changed from external perceptions about patients to internal with a center of attention on patients' personal feelings of disease(23).

1.2 Significance of the Study

Patients after esophagectomy face many problems in all aspects of life (24) but the society at large and the health professionals do not have enough awareness to understand the patients' real conditions and problems of their deteriorated quality of life. (4).To help them out in their miserable period of life the study is needed in our context. The present study is the first one that will identify the areas of problems faced by patients undergone esophagectomy due to cancer. The findings of current study might be helpful for the health professionals as well policymakers to manage and sort out the problems of these patients in a more professional manner by understanding the problems they face which occur after esophageal cancer surgery. So, their quality of life can be improved.

1.3 Rational

Understanding the lived experiences of patients adjusting to lives after esophagectomy is important for healthcare providers. Most of the research has focused on the prevalence of dysphagia and mortality in this population. Several studies have been conducted for measuring the quality of life following surgery but very few qualitative studies on experiences of post-op esophageal cancer patients(4), however, in Pakistan there is no published study available so far.

1.4 Purpose

To know the problems of the participants in detail after esophageal cancer surgery, this study is conducted at the tertiary public sector hospital LRH Peshawar to explore the lived experiences of patients adjusting to lives after esophagectomy.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Changes and challenges

In the chapter accessible literature with respect to changes and challenges faced by esophageal cancer survivors after surgery is discussed. Discussion is then narrowed down to problems and needs of supportive care to adjusting with life after esophagectomy. Literature for a comprehensive study from local, national and international sources are included about the patients adjusting to life after esophagectomy.

2.2 Living life with supporting care after esophagectomy

Illness can be called the experience of a person suffering from symptoms, a description denotes that in which way the disease is perceived and how the individual lived with it (23). Therefore, health care professionals require to have knowledge about the understanding of disease that how it is experienced by the patients afterward in their lives (17,23). It has been also identified that the patients as a challenge experience the new life condition and that the residual symptoms get slow down if they control their feelings in their lives (1). Instead of knowing that the patient's life is exposed to many complications after surgery (1,17) like emotional distress, concerns about their existence and family members' behavior (1). Study shows how physical sufferings extend to psychological manifestations of a person and involving a complete body. Every day nurses along with other staff come across the sufferers. Easing of ill persons always remains the priority of health carer especially a nurse doing care need empathetic perception about the patients' experiences which require a knowledge-based course development taken from the personal experiences of patients(23).

The diagnoses create a crisis, as patients are face up to with a serious disease and need emergency based cure as cancer is an alarm of death so the same produce feelings in the patients that whether they will get well to be alive resultantly they feel pessimistically and get into extreme distressed (1). The state of disturbance puts them tired both mentally as well as physically. Due to the upcoming life uncertainty, their feeling becomes uncontrollable. Living with cancer is like combat against an unpredictable enemy(23). Patients get an immense shock after getting the news about esophageal cancer and its poor prognosis even can get semi suicidal(23). Addressing the post-operation requirements and better knowledge about the patients helping care is needed. The concept of the best possible care of cancer patients is known as supportive care(25). Supportive care helps the patients to survive before the identification of disease during the procedure, treatment throughout the disease and till mourning or death (8). Emotional, informational and instrumental, are the major types of support. The first two deal with that what supportive care is, while the last one means

economy/ status. For helping the patients in supportive care three major perspectives should be adopted (25).

2.3 Accepting physical changes and adjustment with it

Patients suffer from physical problems, severe symptoms, and after surgery complications as they live a limited life rather live a normal life due to their disease. They go through a harsh life and constant effort to survive. The disease leads to change in their looking or appearance built up as well as the working capacity which badly affects the patient's body image and self-confidence(17,23), these changes faced by patients with severity of the disease. Due to the intensity of radiotherapy and after surgery unpleasant effects result in face and neck deformity, the experience of which was upsetting. The noticeable physical changes make the patients as they are not in their own body and make them feel that they are not as they were before connected to their bodies. Patients felt that they are not the persons they used to be(23). Study reports regarding changed features like physical changes in patients because of these types of cancers esophageal, neck, head, intestinal and gastric (17).

2.4 Adjustment with social behavior

Patients feel empty and lonely and go into a social silence following surgery for esophageal cancer. The illness interferes as well disturbed domestic life of patients and of the whole members at home as it confines their everyday lives which discomfort the patients because of self detachment from society. The condition is driven by post-operation complications. All relations whether inhouse or outside ruined (23). The eating habits of the patients get changed on both levels, at home as well outside in public. The patients or the survivors in the beginning after surgery can not control over their body and eating habits, as a result, they can not swallow properly and smoothly, do vomiting and this state take out the survivor from the companionship of relatives and friends. While eating publically they feel uncomfortable and anxious. Some reported to have feeling of being stigmatized due to changed eating habits(17,23). People response towards the survivors' weight and appearance has great impacts on the survivors' health and standards of living in their behavior (17). According to studies cancers like esophageal cancer end in the social isolation as well as solitude. Patients experienced disgustness, and humiliation during talking, food taking, awful breath, facial deformity, and excessive saliva. This adds to the survivors' hesitation to remain intact in the society as feel discomfort in people so they withdraw themselves from society. Patients experienced feelings of being of no worth, no work as they were earlier before the disease. These losses add the separation and of being no value in the society overall (23).

2.5 Adjustment with psychological and emotional changes

Psychiatric problems prevail in survivors initially as well later on with continuity or overtime in spite treatment of esophagus cancer. Surveillance of these survivors is very necessary to provide them or to take adequate steps to help them out when required in psychological disturbances (26). In esophagectomy patients level of psychological problems are unknown, with a related lack of studies on psychological distress by self-report (20). Degradation of mental health strength and as a result falling into the depression is opposite to the body function and cure resultantly the survivors after the surgery show and complain about the extreme mental disturbance, however, the reasons and causes are still not clear and elaborated (20). According to the study hen cancer diagnosed at a stage when the patients are only put on symptomatic treatment they suffer from anxiety whereas on esophagectomy the patients fall into depression in the curing process (26). Another study talks about the difference between cancer and other diseases and explained about the risks that risks of anxiety and depression are two-fold in cancer and compared to other diseases (27).

Anxiety in patients without supporter and carer as well young patients, whereas depression in cancer patients having a number of problems are reportedly very high (20). Patients need support and reassurance postoperatively for they will experience some anxiety and fear after surgery (9). Research shows because of persistent post-operation issues the survivors' pessimistic approach that life has totally altered from all aspects so they feel lonely, upset, under stress and strain and helpless in these situations the need of care, support and help become vital as well essentials (25).

2.6 Health-related Quality of life (HRQL)

Removal of esophagus due to cancer brings countless and miserable impacts on life quality-related health (28). Mass fall of the entire body of patients which affects their all areas of performance is reported. Patients undergoing palliative treatment reported slowly deterioration in most aspects of quality life until death (20). Esophagectomy patients come across several problems of high risk like appetite loss, fatigue, eating and diarrhea which badly affects life quality (29). Due to the increasing development of treatment recently HRQL became accepted and important parameter for the measurement of complications and death ratio in long survivors (8). The rehappening of after surgery complications put long remanning adverse consequences on HRQL in those who survive(30).

2.7 Fear of recurrence and cancer prognosis

Patients after esophagectomy experience gradually poor prognosis (25). Though, there is a balance to be achieved between reliability and introducing hope for long term survival (31). According to a study, most of

the patients after surgery want to know about the general conditions after treatment but due to the specificity of increased prognostic information, it is it turns down (32). Majority of survivors stated that the medical practitioners must ask if an individual desire about the information of prognosis and this directive approach may be the most effective in accepting individual preferences. There is limited evidence of how frequently this occurs in practice (25). One may generally suppose that patients show high fear of recurrence would have a reduced wish for discussions on prognosis, however, on the other hand, these individuals reported a wish for regular and detailed prognostic information and tendency to be actively involved during the consultation(31). Patients reporting high fear of recurrence are more likely to also report the poor quality of life, the authors suggesting the projection of the disease to encourage wish for more information to decrease uncertainty. Esophageal cancer patients appear to require a general level of prognostic information and appreciate an honest approach, while some patients need more positive information in the early postoperative period (20).

Methodology

3.1 Study design

In this study, the qualitative phenomenology study design is used for the in-depth exploration of existing phenomena. The focus remains on in-depth interviews of participants to identify their problems which they experience afterward (33,34).

3.2 Study setting

The study is carried out in department of thoracic surgery Lady Reading hospital Medical Teaching Institution MTI, Peshawar

3.3 Study participants

Participants of this study were those patients who had esophagectomy. They were selected purposively. The participants were from different backgrounds with different standards of living. .

3.4 Inclusion Criteria

- Patients who have undergone surgery for esophageal cancer at least two or more than two months ago.
- Willing to participate in the study.
- Who are stable and above eighteen and below fifty years.
- Both sexes were included

3.5 Exclusion Criteria

- Diagnosed cases of ca esophagus with any other systemic disease e.g hypertension, coronary artery disease, liver diseases, cva etc.

3.6 Sample size

Ten participants' interviews carried out for collection of data to find out their problems which they face after esophageal cancer surgery. Saturation of data was achieved in the tenth interview. All interviews were conducted at Lady Reading Hospital. In qualitative studies sample size is as important as in quantitative but the sample is extracted with different methods (35). In qualitative studies sample size is depending upon "saturation" however sampling will continue until theoretical saturation is not achieved (32,35).

3.8 Method of data collection

The collection of data was through individuals' in-depth interviews. For this purpose, participants were questioned according to interview guide, with open-ended questions. In-depth- face-to-face interviews which were beside notes in handwriting also recorded on audio. Interviews carried out in Pashto. Each interview duration was 40 to 60 minutes. All important remarks of patients were listed in field notebook.

3.9 Analysis of data

Both collection and analysis of data go ahead at the same time. First of all transcriptions and translations were made to interview the individuals in detail. Transcriptions were made under the supervision. Thematic analysis technique (4,32) was adopted for the general understanding of the data by reading and rereading several times each transcript and field notes. The application of codes was used for every line in open codes manner. Similar codes were placed in the same category. From these categories, important themes as well sub-themes were taken out. At the end themes were duly supported by subjects quotes and their narrations. Field notes data was utilized to support the analysis procedure.

Results

Table no 1.2: Theme 2 Psychological effects

Theme	Category	Codes	Data extract
Psychological effects	Mentally uncomfortable	Lack of support to manage grieving.	The problems at the time of operation still persist and I feel very uncomfortable psychologically...am not like before Alas! Alas! what I was before and what I am now alive but dust....(No.1)
	Emotional health	Depression	The situation with me is very pathetic. Yes, I am mentally affected because I got weak and depressed most of the
	Anxiety	A lot of	time. I started depending on

	worries	other...(No.5)
Upset		My tension increases with the situation because the
	Lack of mental support	treatment is so painful and costly too...(No.7)
		I feel uneasy and this change is abrupt. I suddenly feel annoyed and frustrated but become normal with time. I don't feel good in noises. Even when I talk a bit I feel annoyed and frustrated.(No.10)

Table no 1.3: Theme No. 3 Social issues and Support

Theme	Category	Codes	Data extract
Social issues and support.	Lack of social support	Strange behavior of people	People's behavior is like! Strange they avoid to come to see me, to ask about us and our situations. No one is coming! like before, now everything, every relation has gone/ vanished. People used to visit me when I was well off and healthy.... No help, nothing...(No.1)
	Family and relatives conduct	Careless behavior of family and relatives	My relatives, they came to torture me only, realize me how ill I am and my illness makes me weaker; I got worried to think about my health issues. I am even telling my husband not to talk about my cancer... it makes me more worried...(No. 6)
	Couple relationship	Lack of satisfaction from spouse deeds.	My husband nature is ambiguous towards me. He is harsh at times and careless but loves and is caring when is needed. I am not fully satisfied with his behavior. Our relationship is not that strong actually...(No.7)
	Need the help of children.	Feel the non-existence of	

a male
child.

The issues are numberless that are randomly troubling me but the major one is that I don't have any supporting hand I am alone...I need a backbone. I have daughters and no son!! (No.8)

Results

4.1 Introduction

The present study focus was on to explore the lived experiences of patients' who had esophagectomy as part of their esophageal cancer treatment. Ten interviews were conducted and were analyzed. From findings patients, problems were identified, explained and from interview transcriptions direct quotes were presented.

4.2 Results overview

On analyzing the collected data through individuals in depth interviews themes were extracted.

Another problem faced by survivors is psychological. Anxiety, depression, upsetting, disturbed sleep, tension, and mental disturbance.

They also described the problem they face the strange and avoiding behavior of people, no support of relatives as well of the social network.

new changed life situations and adjustment with it. Religious/spiritual aspects, faith in Allah, religious belief, coping and adaptation through spiritual after the esophagectomy.

4.2.1 Physical changes

It is recognized that after the operation for cancer of the esophagus the survivors get effected from many problems which damage their entire life they want and wish to a normal life but due to the damage in their physique experience disability to live normal lives. They adopt physical restrictions in their lives due to this disease. They survive with continuous struggle.

Changes in physical capacity to perform and look of patients damage body image as well self-confidence. The most commonly voiced limitations were of pain, physical discomfort, tiredness, vocal problems, cough, restricted mobility, eating problems, stomach issues and side effects of treatment. One of the respondents stated that:

After the operation, I suffer from chest pain ... (Oh...) I have a problem in sitting and standing....I have hoarseness for two weeks....When I talk too much I get tired my heart gets tired and my throat gets dry... (In pain)...(No.1).

Another respondent shared a similar experience:

I feel pain in the chest...I cough too much... I even started vomiting ... I used to recite Azan (Muazin) but with great disappointment, my voice is no more supporting me to perform my duty... (NO-2).

Surgery for esophageal cancer proposes hope but might impair QOL. Complications after surgery treatment bring severe unease in patients due to less physical activity. Post-op treatment process is very painful resultantly the patients get very weak due to radiation effects. One respondent expressed that:

Doctors treated me with the medicines in the earlier stage of my treatment. Then they recommended operation and then treatment followed by radiotherapy....This radiotherapy was very severe and horrible that makes my nerves weaker... (NO-3).

The physical impairment, ache, weakness, and tiredness, lead to inability in daily work patients experienced. Weakness was experienced by patients as part of their lives continuously due to very feeble strengthless, energyless physique. Because of this state, everything overshadowed as these conditions triggered by the disease itself. One of the respondents described as:

I feel very weak. I am losing my strength day by day The stomach pain is troubling me.....My weakness and stomach issues keep me so upset as..... I do offer prayer but now am unable to stand for long...(NO-8).

I get tired and lost stamina...My fingers get numb and lifeless. I lost my weight and feeling very weak... I can't walk for long even feel tired when sit..... I feel tired when talk..... There are many other physical changes that I feel after the operation... (NO-10).

Internal, structural and functional changes in the esophagus after surgery bring Anatomical changes in esophageal structure and function following surgery causes definite difficulties associated with eating, loss of hunger, less functional capacity to eat, vomiting, malabsorption and stomach issues. Due to this state patients can only enjoy the soft diet and drinks like custard, soups, juices, etc. As said by the patients:

My diet changed with the treatment of the disease.... I usually take soft and light food...But I eat very less because feel tired... (NO-3).

I cannot digest food easily..... I am unable to eat properly the way I ate before..... My diet consists of soft and light food like custard, soup, juices, etc...(NO-4).

Eating problems and the side effects of treatment caused patients to modify the type of food they ate and restrict the diet. Patients were forced to eat mashed or liquid food. Moreover, patients experienced changes in taste and appetite. Lack of appetite or the inability to eat normally caused them to feel depressed and unhappy. Diarrhoea, nausea, vomiting and dumping syndrome were common gastrointestinal problems after surgical and oncological treatment. Most of the patients may not be able to eat properly like before the operation. They face the persistent risk of long-term swallowing, feel tasteless, stomach problems and eating issues. As patients mentioned:

Now I face stomach issue, I cannot eat properly when I take food or drink it makes me discomfort, uneasy and increase my stomach pain (NO-8).

My diet habits changed too.....when eat something I vomit..... I feel that there is some problem with my stomach. I eat less and feel less hungry.... I sometimes feel tasteless; I can't recognize the taste....(NO.10).

4.2.2 Psychological effects

Psychological problems are common among patients with esophageal cancer. Patients undergoing curatively intended treatment for esophageal cancer having significant psychological distress in the form of anxiety, depression, worry, irritation as well as tension and depressed mood. After surgery patients undergo the different stages of crisis reaction. It can be severe and long-lasting psychological symptoms associated with the disease.

In the psychological adapting process, participants had hope and faith and justified all of the difficulties they experienced during treatment and after the operation. Most of the patients experience loneliness and social isolation. Psychological/emotional perspective of new life situation is changed. The individual costs are associated with experiencing the overload of stress, negative emotions, role strain and may lead to psychological health impairment. According to the respondent:

I feel very uncomfortable psychologically... Alas! Alive but not worthy of anything ...I feel so deprived and lonely... I am worried about my life; about my family and children lives...We are in very miserable conditions... This world is merciless no one cares here... (No.1).

Many patients suffering psychological distress throughout treatment and after. Psychological support needed to improve their overall well-being and adaptation to the consequences of this disease and treatment to overcome stress, depression, and tension. Their sleep difficulties progressively worsened due to these conditions. According to the respondent:

I feel sleepless, as I remain disturbed and tense ... I really miss my happy moments when I was healthy spending my time with my kids but now it's different... (No-4).

I lost my happy life after this operation because it brought troubles in my life...I am much worried about my present and coming life.... I feel very helpless! I feel worse going through such situation..... (No-6).

Esophagectomy patients become uncertain about their health recovery and feel that whether they will be having health like they had before the disease or will be able to support themselves and their families which damage their feelings and bring mental problems. According to the respondents' responses:

I am so depressed and under stress..... because being not able to support myself how I would be able to support my family rather need the support of others Oh! What I have become have nothing all has gone.... am a living dead... (No-2).

The situation with me is very pathetic... Yes, I am mentally affected because I got weak and most of the time remains depressed... I am dependent!! Even I am requesting others for my domestic problems to be solved... (No-5).

It has also been shown that some patients are very sensitive to noises that they cannot bear normal talking at home and get this condition is the reason for the mental disturbance of these patients. These survivors because of post-operation problems experience negativity in lives. Derived from patients statements:

I suddenly feel annoyed and frustrated ...I don't feel good in noises. Even when I talk a bit I feel annoyed and frustrated...I feel sleepless and my nights are restless..... (No-10).

4.2.3 Social issues and Support

Social support, that support which is provided by family, friends, relatives, and society. It is very important for the help of patients after the operation to cope with the changes and challenges. For unfortunate diseases like esophagus cancer, the patients need understanding of their conditions and the way they require help and support from the surrounding peoples including family members, friends, colleagues and society they live in. It might be helpful in the speedy recovery of the patients whereas the non-supportive approach of the same escalates the patients' problems which adversely affect the rehabilitation process.

Human beings are called social animals as they need the help and support of each other for the smooth running of lives and such patients need more help and support from their own kinds after this disease and surgery which cause them great mental, physical and financial dent. As per different gathered support sources. Participants stated whenever they

attend any activity or religious gathering in society they do get the support there. Help and understanding are very important in the care of patients later on from all human relations. Some patients shared their experience about the gradual curtailment of their social network due to either the loss of their own strength to keep in touch because of their illness or the avoidance of the people in that network themselves in both cases the things which the participants experienced is agony.

I was having a perfect relationship with my relatives and friends but unfortunately they disconnected with me during my illness that really displeases me ... (NO-4).

Relatives' behavior not good with us after my illness..... Now I feel a change in their behavior too. As I have stopped contacting them due to my illness they too don't bother to visit and share my troubles to give me some relief..... (NO-6).

Serious illness affects family relationships and friendships. Sometimes the illness brings people closer. Sometimes it creates distance both the person with cancer and loves one. It is observed that during the disease and surgery the behaviors of husbands or wives remain very positive in spite of the patients' problem and miserable physical and psychological states. The spouse's help, support, and care play a significant role in the recovery of these patients. As with the help of each other, the patient can recover swiftly in all aspects and do not depend on others. Respondents stated:

The relation between us is normal.... She does all and my personal matters. Without her, I would have been eaten by stray dogs. I am alive because of Allah and because of her... (No-1).

My husband is more caring and loving than before..... But comparatively I am very careless and lost patience but he is totally opposite to my nature..... He treats me like a child; he is very nice to me...(NO-10).

Care and well wishes whether a master or adult child does mean a lot for the sick parents and this approach of children strengthens the will of the patients' endurance towards the recovery. The children's support is important in the smooth and positive recovery process after esophagectomy. Without the support of children, the patients might lose the will to endure towards a healthy life as it is considered that the children are the assets of the parents. According to respondents:

My children love me a lot and are always praying for my good health They show their concern, and they are devoted to me (No-4).

My offsprings are very caring..... They are very worried about me... They treat me as a kid..... (No-6).

We are living in a family-based society where parents are considered to be all authority and men are considered to dominant in times of need and

support. A person having female children only feel so deprived and helpless. One survivor expressed that:

I wish I had a son... Sometimes I cry like a child when I need someone to do something for me....(No-8).

As much as I observed diagnose of cancer changes life completely. The diagnose of cancer brings severe shock, stress and bad feeling about life as the patient starts believing that this disease is “killing knife”. Cancer diagnose is like being given a death sentence and stigma in the society and patients family tried to hide the diagnose. One informant said:

Only my two cousins were aware of my illness. No other person knew about my cancer, even I was unaware of it, that I am suffering from it.....(NO-2).

The doctor told my husband that I have esophageal cancer and after knowing this I got upset..... My husband was hiding it..... But I kept asking, insisting to tell me the reality as I will accept it, considering it my fate.....(NO-4).

4.2.4 Financial Issues

Patients of esophageal cancer suffer financially a lot if from poor backgrounds and third world country like Pakistan where most of the population lived under poverty level because neither they can support themselves nor there is any government program especially designed to support patients financially that's way due to the reason mentioned these patients live a very miserable lives rather the entire family suffers a lot. Many families adopted more than one coping mechanism to overcome financial crises.

Financial problems and basic money related requirements of life badly influence the quality of life in post oesophagectomy patients as the treatment of the disease is very costly and the disease is common in people in the middle-lower class who cannot bear the expenses for long. These people even sell out their houses, land, valuable things, their cattle and all savings for their cure. Unbearable charges which include charges beyond one financial status is linked to slow adherence of cancer treatment. Delay and to forgo follow up of patients under cancer treatment have unpleasant consequences and make the treatment less effective so short survival. As respondent told:

Everything vanished due to this sickness.... We have no money ...Before I had some savings now I have nothing Dr advice me nutritional supplement and medicine but I have no money so, left without any treatment... (NO-1).

My son borrowed money for me because a lot of money is spent on my treatment. ... no one to helps me out financially... (NO-2).

What I had have been spent on my treatment and praying to Almighty Allah to support me I sell my lands and spend the money on my treatment as the treatment is expensive. No one helps me... (NO-8).

Patients following surgery must be helped out in all aspects. Whatever they need, they must be helped out. Majority of participants stated that the maximum favor should be given to them. The results and adverse effects of cancer remain for long. Most of the survivors needed to be aware of the disease they have and not being able to work properly like before in future after operation. That's why they were extremely bothered that how without any financial help they will be able to maintain their economy. Most of patients stated that they need support from the healthcare system because they cannot afford such expansive treatment.

I am no more able to earn money. But I will take advice from my doctors whether I am able of cycling or not because I used to sell shoppers so I could continue my work. I will discuss this with my doctor after my electric shocks.....(NO-7).

Most of these patients face a lot of difficulties as they do not have other helping hands except their family who also becomes busy with these patients at hospital and cannot do their jobs whatever they do properly which damage their financial condition badly in long term in way of their treatment due to which they cannot afford the expenses of treatment.

...Treatment is tough and expensive being poor it was and is difficult for me to afford it.... My husband is spending and selling everything for my treatment..... Now-a-days he spent time with me taking care of me doing nothing....(NO-4).

Esophageal cancer patients are also among the very unfortunate human because of this disease the patients not only got damaged physically but due to the very expensive treatment they face severe socioeconomic, financial and psychological problems after the surgery.

It is not a blessed life. My weak body and less finance are making it more miserable... (NO- 5).

..... I am helpless... due to our poverty, my funeral expenses will be impossible for my family..... (NO-6).

4.2.5 Acceptance and adjustment to a new changed way of life

The patients' acceptance of the fact that they are facing a very unfortunate disease but do not give up and fight with it with a positive approach that they can live normal lives. Their positive approach brings them close to Creator as when a person accepts their physical condition and remain hopeful that after all the medical treatments the only hope remains is that, if they had healthy lives once, can live with this disease in a healthy manner with the help of same Creator "Allah". With this positive approach, they turned to Allah, do worship and remain calm believe that there is no one

more kind than Allah. So the survivors own positive approach converts their anger as well agony into contentment.

Patients following esophageal cancer surgery have a substantial impact on entire life. Spiritual well-being that addresses not only religious issues but also pain and symptom control and the potentially damaging effects of advanced disease on self-worth and close relationships. The spiritually informed clinical encounter may be one in which sufficient time and opportunity for reflection are afforded to consider illness and treatment decisions in the context of religious beliefs and personal values, self-worth, support systems and concerns about dependency. Life-threatening sickness like esophageal cancer may become a spiritual encounter and a deep emotional experience for cancer survivors as they cope and find a path to healing. They have a belief that all the fortunes and misfortunes, health and illness, life and death are from the creator of this world "Allah". Spirituality and faith induce in patients the sources to find the required inner strengths, which includes rituals, perspective thinking for exceeding immediate physical condition and modalities of coping with their oncological sickness.

According to the participants:

Oh! What can I do; all night I spend sitting, weep and pray before Allah... All this luck from Allah, it is not from the human... Allah has given me this disease and Allah will give me health also... Inshallah! (NO- 1).

My problems will be solved if Allah wants..... I have strong faith in Allah, He is the Creator and He knows better why He put me in this condition and I know there would be reason behind my sufferings and I am sure He will bless me with healthy life...(NO- 6).

Cancer survivors face spiritual and role strain issues involving their belief, their perceived relationship with Allah and the possibility and meaning of death. Being a fatal disease cancer brings too many changes in a patient life and one of which spiritual changes in religious beliefs and religious practices.

I want to live a long but happy life without pains and troubles I am in need of special prayers. May Allah bless me with healthy life (NO—3).

I believe no one can escape from death. It is all about the time that is fixed for death.... (NO- 2).

Being Muslims having belief and hope in Allah. In spite of life taking disease, they look to words Allah with the hope that if the Master can give death after life will also give life after death and health after sickness. The believers of Allah firmly believe that they will be fine only if Allah wishes.

I am still hopeful for the bright side..... Allah will bless me with health again and will have a normal life. We cannot avoid being ill because

illness is the part of life.....Grief is attached with the joy, same as death (NO- 5).

Discussion

5.1 Introduction

The present study conducted for exploration lived experiences after esophagectomy in patients that how they strive to adjust. On focusing the aim of the study participants' experiences were explored by questioning regarding their issues adjusting to lives after their surgery for esophageal cancer. Psychological effects, Social issues and Support,

5.2 Physical changes

The only choice to treat cancer of esophagus left to the patients is esophagectomy as the procedure is very exhaustive and painful that's why cause numerous complications after surgery (28). The initial changes or complications after esophagectomy the participants felt about were physical changes. Patients' undergone esophagectomy face constant and continuous problems with physical function and specific symptoms. Study participants were expressing about having poor health conditions and limitations in the ability to perform daily life activities, other functional disabilities and an inability to work due to their weak health condition. All the participants reported similar factors which become hurdles in their daily basis work and activities are fatigue and pain. Although the participants got operated for esophageal cancer they added that even then they are dependent on the high types of pain killers for the pain is not subsided fully. The participants mentioned about their everyday symptoms of tiredness and strengthlessness as fatigue controls all things which are the disease reasons. According to a study, esophagectomy is major surgery and the most traumatic surgical procedure as its complications can lead to patient discomfort (37,38). Participants described the ongoing difficulties they experienced, these included weight loss, reduced capacity to eat, nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, bloating, shortness of breath and feeling the cold. Another study states that giving complete support and encouraging the patients during the fight after surgery with symptoms of pain, dysphagea, loss of appetite and other physical changes are very essential and important (11,39-43).

It is recognized in the current study that there are pre and post side effects of both cancer and its treatment. Problems like difficulty in swallowing, dietary alterations, eating restrictions, reflux, dry mouth, taste, coughing and appetite loss are the most common. According to a study, most of the patients may not be able to eat exactly as they did before their operation for their feelings cannot satisfy them to eat or not to eat even if they are hungry(28,41,44).

5.3 Psychological effects

Esophageal Cancer survivors stated about their experience of decreased quality of life due to psychological problems. Study also indicates that many patients facing psychological problems following esophageal cancer surgery (27,45) and the prevalence of psychological problems in cancer survivors range 10 to 38% associated with poor survival rate (46). Moreover, the patients with the diagnosis of cancer and its treatment live with emotional stress. Patients also live with common worries, uncertainty, fears that in times to come, and they won't be able to make future strategies. Other worries such as patients role in family and rest of the relations will be completely changed. Some patients reported that due to this anxiety they get angry to remain depressed also isolated and self-respect lessness. Living with experiences of cancer extremely stressful (30,41,47).

The majority of participants with post-op psychiatric issues were suffering from depression or anxiety and it also disturbs their personal family life. Studies show that among survivors of cancers psychological impairment exist such as a disability in occupational performance, anxiety, depression and disrupted conjugal relations are more common (40,48,49). As per this study, esophageal cancer surgery changed the lives of the participants totally by bringing very tough, stressful and tragic circumstances in their lives. Other studies also confirm that in cancer survivors the most significant prospect which is common worldwide considered as mental disturbance an uprising cause that plays an important part in cancer prognosis(47).

5.4 Social issues and Support

The diagnose and esophageal cancer cure cause bodily and psychological changes and affect the cancer survivors entire social life such as family life, other relationships, work, income and rest of the activities. According to studies cancer survivors have social difficulties in everyday life (47,48). Cancer patients deal and face multiple problems due to the disease and its treatment. An earlier study shows that survivors become dependant on others help to overcome psychological and social troubles as they experience negative consequences mentally with degraded life quality (50,51).

Many patients reported decreased physical role and social function. Serious illness affects family and friends relationships. Sometimes the illness brings people closer. Sometimes it creates distances in both persons with cancer and their loved ones for certain reasons. One of the reason is the power or energy of others to support such people. Survivors experienced that network of friends who once were energy and support during healthy days now shrank either due to their own lack of energy or due to the increase of needs of illness of the survivors. The same was

experienced as great grief by the participants in times when they were badly needed the support and energy of that social network. Some of the participants experienced intensified support and care after the surgery from both family and social network. When an individual gets sufficient informal help from the people next door, relatives, colleagues, and friends, etc. This could help the patients in the performance of important responsibilities whereas in case of no positive informal caring from the aforesaid the survivors' psychosocial issues get worse. Study shows that psychosocial distress is thought to be the basic problem rising in patients which perform the main function of malignant disease prognosis (47).

To help out the survivors in their supposed responsibilities can result in the adjustment of survivors with situations they face. Indulgent as well support is an essential element to fight the post-operation difficulties occur due to the deterioration of survivors health which becomes very challenging for the cancer survivors whereof they require the help and care from relatives, friends, and colleagues that is to say social network. Because of this approach cancer survivors do not feel alone and helpless due to the social net work in field for their helping with the sense of best human kindness. In case of cancer survivors earlier study talk about the essentiality and importance of members from family for the care of survivors (25).

5.5 Financial issues

A person living with cancer face significant financial troubles. These troubles increase in persons with advanced stage of the disease who are from poor backgrounds live in faraway areas or villages. Poor economic stress is the result of joblessness, low earning or no earning, high treatment expenses end in significant mental torture or stress. Cancer survivors experience decreased financial status (47,52). Financial problems due to treatment of disease significantly disrupt the families and patients as they make hurdles in taking treatment. Financial problems may be an impediment to treatment or preventive care. Participants have also difficulty in making financial arrangements for treatment. One study shows that due to cancer many complications occur as its treatment is very expensive (47,53). The struggle to run the house with raised needs of treatment expenses due to the disease through loans or movable and immovable properties sale out. Many participants adopted more than one way to overcome the financial distress; the most common of them is taking a loan, the social network helps, using savings, selling financial assets. Study indicates that those survivors who have low socioeconomic status face more financial problems for cancer treatment(54) and mostly sell assets or borrow to a very great extent to finance their expenditures (53,55).

Patients who are living with diagnosed malignancy have high financial crash. Determining factors are family income, help from the outsources and disease extent. There are many reasons of financial burdens related to cancer treatment such as considerable high cost of radiation, chemotherapy, surgery, treatment center travel and health care at home. According to earlier study the survivors more repeated complaints were related to disease cause financial problems (52,54,56). If members of the family take out time from their labor or job the finance of home running get disturbed. Participants also reported cancer-related financial problems. Financial problems badly affected the treatment and access to care. Besides the physical and psychosocial impacts, financial problems due to cancer negatively affect survivors. Study shows that reasons of stress and depression are caused due to the fiscal status difficulties of patients. Economic stress is negatively linked with survivors QOL (56-58).

5.6 Acceptance and adjustment to a new changed way of life

The new life situation after esophagectomy is frightening and very painful for the patients and to adjust with this new life they need spiritual and mental power to live comparatively contended. It is a reality that patients have undergone surgery for esophageal cancer, suffer a lot that affect their lives badly for a long time even till death and they experience this new life situation as a continuous unendable struggle to survive and to survive in a positive manner they need spiritual and religious therapy from the surrounding people they live with and from within themselves. Studies show that medical practitioners should extend their practice beyond medical care and should advise the patients about spiritual and religious aspects(59). Finding out the reality and definition of life in stress full situations by mankind is called spiritual management (60,61). According to participants when they got informed about the disease they were highly shocked and were very disappointed and begun to fear death with change view about life and that's why they try to get cope with their new conditions and in this way, the great need of spiritual and other believes took place. Study shows that patients turn towards religious understandings that all good and evil come from heaven and the only options to overcome the situations is the acceptance of heaven will. That's how spirituality becomes the source of coping with the new changed way of life (60,61).

To deal with cancer or its pressure the right way for the survivors' mental health is adopting spirituality as the main component. Life-threatening diseases creat sensitivity in patients with questions that why I have been created or whether the only purpose of my life was this one due to these factors of life meaning and purpose the only thing that improves their life quality is spirituality. Being religious the people of this area turn toward more religious practices during times of problems and severe stress.

Study indicates that patients who know about the creation and aim of their lives have more positive approach of attaining health and have certainty of better life quality in spite of the disease (52). According to another study cancer also brings spiritual changes in religious beliefs and religious practices. Belief and religion as a common remedy play a vital part in the concepts of patients how to cope with trauma of disease. Individual seek spiritual support and religious ways to manage traumatic and challenging life events (49,61).

Majority of participants reported that spirituality is an important source of support during their sickness. They believe that Allah is the Almighty. He is the one Who did it to them and He is the one Who got the power to settle it, besides the treatment and medicine. This illness is a part of God's will. Spiritual support from God was realized as they talked and prayed to him. Study indicates that religious patients feel and believe that God is there and will help them as always more than mankind. Prayers become very important to them(61).

Conclusion

Esophageal cancer is a threat worldwide and its treatment is esophagectomy. The patients after surgery face problems identified in this research as esophagectomy is a complex surgery and bring many changes to patients' lives. It becomes hard to adjust to life. To treat, care and do proper counseling of such patients require to much time and knowledge about the problems of these patients to make an effective plan for helping them in a more professional and human manner is necessary. The findings of this study are based on the problems of the patients with suggestions how to improve life quality of survivors after surgery of esophagus cancer through the best of human capability and capacity.

Implications and conclusion

6.1 Introduction

Exploring patients problems after esophagectomy faced during the process of adjusting to life is the purpose of current study. The data was collected at Lady Reading Hospital Peshawar through in-depth individuals' interviews and after the detailed analysis problems of patients were identified. This chapter focuses on conclusions drawn from study findings, implications of findings in nursing practice, education, and research.

6.2 Implications of findings

The study is the first one to find and determine the problems and lived experiences of patients who come across and face them after esophageal cancer surgery in public sector hospital Peshawar. This study will help to a great extent the health professionals at hospitals. On the basis of the current study and identified problems, the nurses will be able to manage the patients at hospitals as:

- To understanding the lived experiences of patients and highlight them.
- To care the patients in a more proper manner.
- To find out the patients existing feelings.
- To help out the policymakers to make a welfare policy for such patients.
- To guide the relatives of the patients and society.

6.2.1 Nursing Practice

Identified problems of post-operation esophageal cancer patients in public sector hospital Peshawar may help in developing a proper policy by the policymakers for the welfare of these patients and practice guidelines for the nurses to ensure its implementation.

6.2.2 Nursing Education

- The findings of the current study will help the nurse educators as well as curriculum developers to include it at the basic level of nursing education and the following specialty doers in nursing.
- It may also help the health professionals for the better care of esophageal cancer patients after operation.

6.2.3 Nursing Research

The findings of this study may help and encourage the other researchers in nursing to conduct study on such patients which will help to explore other aspects of patients' problems which will have a positive impact on the overall improvement of patients care.

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